

Solar Energy Based Smart Green Village

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Abstract— Modern civilization is what has resulted from the use of energy. The more energy used, the better developed the nation is. And by dumping significant amounts of carbon into the atmosphere each day, which causes our planet to get warmer by the day, this addiction to progress and civilization is also courting its demise. We need to stop relying on fossil fuels right away if we want to rescue our civilization and the planet, which is where the term "renewable energy" comes in. The best economically viable solution among all renewable energy sources is solar electricity. Solar Panels are the key component of producing solar energy. But, the limitation in this situation is that single panels of this kind cannot create large amounts of power without being coupled in a number of parallel or series configurations, which is not at all space- friendly. Yet, by putting in more solar panels, we can handle the increased load. i.e. electricity is in more demand. While the power is being given, it should be remembered that the batteries must be linked in both series and parallel in order to maintain the voltage and the current supply .Furthermore Necessary Are proper inverter ratings .Another Top Priority Is safety, which calls for the installation of a rated fuse and sufficient component isolation. Due to their propensity to heat up when operating, the batteries and inverters must be positioned in a well- ventilated area or room. The solar panels need to be kept in an area that receives plenty of sunshine. At both the installation and maintenance levels, periodic maintenance is also necessary, as is proper supervision.

Index Terms—

Inverters, Renewable energy, Solar Charge Controller, Solar Panels

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional energy sources such as coal, petroleum, and natural gases are rapidly depleting and causing detrimental effects on the environment by releasing harmful gases into the atmosphere. As the world faces an energy crisis, it is crucial to adopt green energy sources that are readily available in nature and do not pose any harm to the environment. India, with a population of 1.35 billion people, faces challenges in providing access to water and electricity, making it difficult to rely on conventional energy sources. Therefore, it is imperative to shift to abundant and sustainable energy sources, such as solar energy, which can provide electricity without harming the environment. This project aims to provide renewable energy solutions for villages in India where access to electricity is a luxury, by utilizing solar energy to meet their electricity needs and promote environmental sustainability.

II. MATERIALS REQUIRED

Solar energy is the primary source of energy being utilized, which involves the use of solar panels, battery packs, solar charger, and an inverter [3]. The Solar Panels Produce Electricity, which is transferred to the solar charger for stabilization and storage in the batteries. The inverter then draws the power from either the solar charger or batteries and converts it into

AC power for household equipment to operate. Photovoltaic cells, made of semiconducting materials such as silicon, are present in solar panels and generate direct current energy when exposed to sunlight. This energy is further converted into alternating current energy through the inverter, which flows through the home's panel and is proportionately distributed. The circuit incorporates an MPPT solar charge controller, short for Maximum Power Point Tracking, which efficiently extracts the maximum power from the solar panels and charges the batteries at an efficiency of up to 96%. For devices that require more power to operate than direct current energy can provide, the circuit employs an inverter that converts direct current energy into alternating current energy at a given frequency and voltage. The alternating energy can be distributed in homes and industries, as shown in Fig.1. Overall, the use of solar power can be advantageous for long-term energy efficiency.

Fig.1. Block Diagram of the system.

Fig.2.Circuit Diagram of the system.

III.SYSTEM INSTALLATION

- The project requires the connection of 20 solar panels in a series-parallel combination, each with a capacity of 300 watts, resulting in a total capacity of 6,000 watts.
- A solar charge controller rated at 24 volts and 6000 watts must be connected to the solar panels to distribute power.
- Each solar panel has a fuse to ensure protection.
- The charge controller is set to 24 volts and 10 amperes, which charges the battery with the flip of a switch in the circuit.
- To ensure battery safety, a rated fuse is also connected.
- The solar charger is directly connected to the inverter to receive a direct power supply throughout the day.
- The inverter converts the DC power to 100-290 volts, 5 amperes, 50 hertz supply that can be supplied to the main switch to power household appliances.
- The power generated by the solar panels will be available for 6-10 hours.
- The essential loads for a single house include 4 tube lights, 4 fans, 1 refrigerator unit, and 1 television set.
- The battery charger connected to the MPPT solar charger can also charge various batteries used in agricultural equipment [6-8].

- The connection diagram is shown in Figure 2.

IV.LOAD CALCULATION

For a single house with following specifications, the total load can be calculated as outlined below.

- 1 tube light consumes power=40W
- 4tube lights consume power=(40×4)=160W
- 4tube lights running for 12 hours=(160×12)= 1920WH
- 4 ceiling fan consume power =(80×4)=320W
- 1 ceiling fan consumes power=80W
- 4 ceiling fans running for 20 hours=(320×20)= 6400WH
- 1 refrigerator consumes power =250W
- 1 refrigerator running for 24 hours=(250×24)= 6000WH

Total Power Consumed=(1920+6400+360+6000)=14680 WH=14.68KWH

Fig. 3.Amount in rupees vs Number of years.

**TABLE I
COST ANALYSIS**

SL NO.	MATERIAL LIST	COST(in INR)
1	SOLAR PANELS	1,64,000/-
2	SOLAR CHARGE CONTROLLER	44,650/-
3	TOGGLE SWITCH	84/-
4	BATTERY	6,620/-
5	INVERTER	8,300/-
6	EXTERNAL BATTERY CHARGER	8,360/-
	TOTAL EXPENSES	2,32,014/-

V.COST ANALYSIS:

Table 1 presents a comprehensive cost analysis, revealing that the total cost for constructing one house amounts to approximately Rs.2,32,014/-. Research has shown that solar panels have an estimated lifespan of 25 years, which suggests that the expenses incurred can be recouped within a span of 9-10 years. This is further supported by Figure 3, which illustrates the relationship between the initial investment in installation and electricity bills over the years until the investment is fully recovered. As depicted in the graph, the curve levels off at the beginning of the 10th year, indicating that the investment becomes profitable and returns within a 10-year timeframe.

CONCLUSION

Renewable Energy Is Considered To Be Safe,Clean,and sustainable source of energy.Additionally,using renewable energy can bring remarkable economic benefits to any industry. Solar Power, for instance,is an endless source of readily available energy that can also generate other energy resources. Almost all areas of the Earth's surface receive sufficient solar energy to harness it. Using solar energy in a systematic manner is the only way to ensure sustainable renewable energy. Our project is a small-scale initiative aimed at providing affordable electricity to areas in India where it is considered a luxury. By using solar panels, we can reduce electricity costs while promoting environmental cleanliness through the use of non-conventional energy sources. Our analysis shows that this project is cost-effective, with minimal maintenancerequired.Althoughtheinitialcostsmaybehigherforeconomicallydisadvantaged

sectors, we estimate that the investment will be recouped within 9-10 years. According to our research, there are three types of solar panels: Monocrystalline, Polycrystalline, and Thin film (Cadmium Telluride, Cd, Te). Monocrystalline is currently the most used type due to its high productivity, despite its higher cost. However, Thin-film or Cadmium Telluride may become a more cost-effective alternative with further research and analysis in the future.

Acknowledgment

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